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"Social Media: The Demon Inside A Person's Head"

Social media addiction encourages cyberbullying, online harassment, and negatively affects eyesight, leading to low self-esteem and a lack of productivity.

Is social media really beneficial, or is it the demon inside your head? Is it the voice that fills your mind with negativity, making your once angelic face fade? How can you stay up all night talking about someone else's life but fail to fix your own? You say you're scared of monsters, yet you never acknowledge the one inside your head. Wake up, kid! The demon is inside your head!

Social media addiction is becoming increasingly common. Many studies have found that excessive social media use can affect a person both physically and mentally, and it also impacts students' academic performance. The world of social media is full of chaos—it ruins lives through online harassment, mockery, and even threats, leading to mental health issues such as suicidal ideation and attempts.

Cyberbullying is a form of bullying that often occurs on social media. It includes harassment, invading someone's privacy, and other illegal acts carried out through digital platforms. Many cases of cyberbullying arise because of social media. Celebrities, teenagers, young adults, members of the LGBTQ+ community, and even persons with disabilities—these individuals have all experienced cyberbullying. According to the 2023 Youth Risk Behavior Surveillance System, 16% of high school students reported being electronically bullied within the 12 months prior to the survey. This is alarming, as some victims attempted suicide due to the humiliation caused by cyberbullying. This issue led to the creation of **Republic Act No. 10175**, or the **Cybercrime Prevention Act of 2012**, which defines cybercrimes and mandates the prohibition of cybersex.

According to studies, there are **6.9 billion mobile users** worldwide—almost equivalent to the global population. Excessive screen time can lead to eye problems such as blurred vision, red eyes, itchiness, and dryness. Research shows that **39.7% of smartphone users** are at

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a higher risk of developing eye problems due to excessive digital device use. This can also increase expenses, as affected individuals may need to consult doctors and purchase eyeglasses or contact lenses to maintain clear vision. Additionally, prolonged gadget use has been linked to various health problems, including dizziness, headaches, and sleep disturbances.

Some people argue that social media benefits us in many ways. Platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, and X allow us to communicate with loved ones, friends, and acquaintances, regardless of distance. We can share updates about our lives, keeping our connections strong even when separated. However, social media can also be a source of negative effects on both our physical and mental well-being. It can influence bad behavior and disrupt healthy habits.

Moreover, excessive social media use can lead to addiction, affecting our behavior, sleep patterns, academic focus, and real-life relationships. Comparing ourselves to others on social media can significantly impact our self-esteem, making us feel anxious, depressed, and inadequate.

In conclusion, while social media has its benefits, it also poses significant risks to our physical, mental, and emotional health. The increasing rates of depression, anxiety, sleep deprivation, online harassment, and cyberbullying are alarming consequences of overuse. These harmful effects remind us to be cautious about what we share online and to take responsibility for the potential consequences. Instead of being consumed by social media, which often brings more harm than good, we should focus on what truly matters—engaging in physical activities, eating healthily, improving productivity, and living a balanced and fulfilling life.

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